

Subject: Fw: Williamson Collection

Date: Sat, 10 Aug 2002 16:01:24 +0100

From: "Derek Kennet" <derek.kennet@durham.ac.uk>

To: "Priestman, Seth" <seth.priestman@durham.ac.uk>

Dear Seth

A reply from Whitehouse (and mine to him). Not much help really.

Derek

----- Original Message -----

From: Derek Kennet <derek.kennet@durham.ac.uk>

To: WhitehouDB <WhitehouDB@cmog.org>

Sent: Saturday, August 10, 2002 3:57 PM

Subject: Re: Williamson Collection

> Dear Dr Whitehouse,
>
> Many thanks for your helpful comments.
>
> We do have here all of Williamson's papers, cards & photos that the
> Ashmolean holds. We have been right through them all - but no maps. It is
> also clear that a number of the crucial notebooks are missing. My feeling
> is
> that these items, the core of the survey documentation, have been removed.
> This could have happened either before or after the material was deposited
> in the Ashmo., no inventory was ever made so we might never know.
>
> I'm not sure who might have taken this material, but I think that Martha
> Prickett is a possibility. She may have needed it for the completion of
> her
> PhD. As you may have heard she died two years back, of breast cancer. We
> are
> trying to chase up her papers (now apparently with her brother in
> Philadelphia).
>
> It is a real pity that the archive is not complete. It also means that the
> precise location of about 50% of Williamson's sites are lost.
>
> Please do let us know if you can think of anywhere else they might have
> ended up.
>
> Otherwise the work is progressing well and I am confident that the
> material
> will still make a very useful contribution to Iranian & Gulf archaeology.
> We
> hope to have the first phase of the work completed by January 2003.

> Yours

> Derek Kennet

> ----- Original Message -----

> From: WhitehouDB <WhitehouDB@cmog.org>

> To: 'Derek Kennet' <derek.kennet@durham.ac.uk>

> Sent: Saturday, August 10, 2002 3:19 PM

> Subject: RE: Williamson Collection

>> Dear Dr. Kennet:

>> Many thanks for your message.

>> I do not know the answers to your questions.

>> However, having known Andrew, it would surprise me if he did not collect
>> material from every site he visited, regardless of date, although it is
>> possible that he deliberately did not revisit known prehistoric sites.

>> Unlike the Arabian side, the Iranian coast of the Gulf seems to have few
 >> prehistoric sites - at least, few have been located - perhaps as a
 result
 > of
 >> the evolution of the Gulf itself (a wild guess on my part!).
 >>
 >> At the time of Andrew's surveys, the best available large-scale maps
 were
 >> those used by the Gendarmerie, which were available as large
 photocopies.
 > I
 >> know that Andrew used "Gendarme maps," although I have no idea whether
 he
 >> was able to acquire them for all the areas he surveyed. My guess is
 that
 >> whenever possible he marked the locations of sites on these maps.
 Another
 >> source of good (actually, better), large-scale maps was the then Iranian
 >> National Oil Company (I have maps covering the Siraf region) and Andrew
 > may
 >> have had access to these. In either case, it would surprise me if
 Andrew
 >> did not keep, in addition to well-nigh illegible notes, annotated maps.
 > Do
 >> you have his papers or are they possibly at the Ashmolean?
 >>
 >> I am sorry I cannot be more helpful.
 >>
 >> David Whitehouse
 >> -----Original Message-----
 >> From: Derek Kennet [mailto:derek.kennet@durham.ac.uk]
 >> Sent: Friday, August 09, 2002 7:00 AM
 >> To: WhitehouDB
 >> Subject: Williamson Collection
 >>
 >> Dear Dr Whitehouse,
 >>
 >> You may remember that I contacted you last October regarding our work on
 >> the
 >> Williamson Collection. Work is progressing well. We are presently trying
 >> to
 >> locate the sites that he collected from. You mentioned that we should
 >> contact you if we had any specific questions about Williamson's work.
 >>
 >> I have two questions that you may be able to help with:
 >>
 >> 1. We are unsure of Williamson's policy on pre-Sasanian pottery. There
 is
 >> very little of it in the collection. It is possible that: a) there was
 >> none
 >> in the area he worked in (unlikely), b) he did not collect it, c) he
 >> collected it and it has been separated and is stored somewhere else
 (with
 >> M
 >> Prickett's material?, at Tepe Yayha?, at the archaeology museum in
 >> Tehran?).
 >> Do you have any knowledge about Williamson's pre-historic collection
 >> strategy and, if he collected pre-historic pottery, where it might now
 be?
 >>
 >> 2. Locating Williamson's sites is very difficult as there are no maps or
 >> notebooks that give the site locations. All we have is a series of cards
 >> with site numbers and occasional toponyms. Did Williamson keep maps? We
 >> assume he must have done. Do you have any copies of or know where they
 may
 >> be?
 >>
 >> I have spoken about this to a number of people who knew and worked with
 >> Williamson
 >> (Prof Lamberg-Karlovsky, Don Whitcomb, Prof Hillenbrand etc). I have
 also
 >> contacted Prof Sumner.
 >>
 >> Many thanks for your time.
 >>